

European Network for Biodiversity Information (ENBI)

ENBI Forums: final report

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2. Introductory summary

ENBI Forums developed a communication space and a set of resources and activities to bring together experts and end-users in specific fields of interest, facilitate information exchange and promote cooperation. The output has been to contribute to build a stronger network among all of those involved in biodiversity information in Europe as a mean for increased efficiency in this area and to contribute to GBIF.

ENBI forums has developed its activities along three lines:

ENBI Forums website (<http://www.enbi.info/forums/>). It comprises several information and communication resources (events calendar; expertise database; information on European museums, collections, projects, thematic networks; and GBIF nodes), as well as details about the participation, contents and inputs of the e-conferences and workshops. It also provides links and "roadmaps" to all public ENBI documents kept in the CIRCA System.

ENBI CIRCA Virtual Community. ENBI Forums provided other ENBI work packages and the ENBI Community at large with a communication space, through CIRCA "[Interest Groups](#)". The CIRCA libraries are used as a permanent repository of ENBI's documents and other outcomes accessible to everybody. See <http://www.enbi.info/forums/ig/cep.php>

Discussion and networking events. The three electronic conferences organized, hosted and carried out have been one of the main discussion forums provided by ENBI. These events have involved nearly two hundred scientists and other biodiversity stakeholders to discuss on relevant topics for the community and GBIF such as:

- Open-access for biodiversity information.
- Data validation and restrictions in the GBIF network
- Improving European participation in GBIF.

On the basis of the discussion and conclusions documents of these e-conferences two workshops were carried out on the following selected focuses:

- Promoting access to Biodiversity Information: balancing needs of users and providers.
- Improving European participation in GBIF: The participants' point of view.

These events served a number of purposes, not the least to gather together European GBIF nodes to foster knowledge-transfer and further cooperation among them.

The contributions and reports, as well as the lessons learned on how to organize e-conferences are all accessible after the conclusion of ENBI through the ENBI Forums pages:

<http://www.enbi.info/forums/ig/cep.php>

3. ENBI WP2 Website

The ENBI Forums site (<http://www.enbi.info/forums/>) has been now in place for almost three years and it is regularly updated. The Site comprises several information and communication resources (Events calendar; Expertise database; European museums & collections; Related projects & thematic networks; and European and Non-European GBIF nodes), as well as links to the VC, information about the participation, contents and inputs of the e-conferences and workshops and provide external links to all public ENBI documents kept in the CIRCA System.

During the 2nd year we introduced some improvement in the service. We changed the general format and programming to make it more compatible with different web browsers as well, to make better use of different screen resolutions.

As part of supporting other ENBI Partners, ENBI Forums has also developed, updated and maintained the ENBI general site (www.enbi.info), in technical underlying aspects as well as in format and maintenance of external links.

The website in its current state comprises a total of forty pages and has provided information and links to 554 events on biodiversity: conferences, symposiums, workshops, congresses relevant in the European context. We also investigated and pursued how to increase the ENBI website relevance in the searching engines. Some success indicators of this exercise are: ENBI project is on the first place when we look up by "ENBI" and there are 123 pages with links to the ENBI web site (www.enbi.info). The ENBI website shows up in third place when searching by "European Biodiversity".

ENBI Glossary of terms, acronyms and organizations. Carried out by WPs 3 and 12 is operational at <http://www.s2you.com/platform/projects/enbi/glossary/index.do>

4. ENBI CIRCA Virtual Community

The CIRCA tool (developed by the EU, and used also by GBIF) was chosen to develop a virtual space to share all contents and discussions of ENBI community (M2.1, D2.1). ENBI VC is thus placed in a subdirectory of the GBIF CIRCA area (<http://circa.gbif.net/enbi/>). CIRCA allows using members created directly in the ENBI CIRCA directory, as well as including some previously stored in the EIONET directory. Although several problems have appeared during the use of this tool, at present ENBI CIRCA VC comprises 344 members, and 17 Interest Groups (IGs).

Relevant documents have been shared in these Interest Groups and can be accessed depending on access restrictions and the privileges of each user. For example, whilst the full contents of the discussions carried out in the 1st e-conference are fully accessible by any user (either registered or not; D2.4), the ENBI inner management documents included in the steer IG are accessible only to the small number of persons (mainly WP leaders) that belong to it.

Every IG has a directory of members and a library, with documents, images, links, etc. There is already an important collection of public documents and work package deliverables accessible from ENBI Community Library IG. Some documents are access-restricted (internal administrative documents, preliminary reports of work packages, drafts of current studies...).

IG Name	Acronym	Explanation
1st ENBI e-conference	Econ1	First ENBI e-conference
1st ENBI Workshop	ws1	First ENBI Workshop (25 - 28 May 2004)
2nd ENBI e-conference	Econ2	Second ENBI e-conference (9 - 24 March 2004)
2nd ENBI Forums workshop		Second ENBI Forums Workshop
3rd ENBI e-conference		Third ENBI e-conference: Improving European participation in GBIF (14 - 28 February 2005)
Cluster II	Cluster2	Maintenance, enhancement and presentation of biodiversity databases
Cluster III e-conference tests	Clust3	Data integration, interoperability and analysis Tests about the use of ENBI CIRCA for moderated electronic conferences
ENBI community	comm.	A general communication and information platform for ENBI members and interested non-members.
ENBI members	Memb	An Interest Group for network management purposes. This IG only accommodates the official members of ENBI.
ENBI steering / management committee	Steer	An Interest Group for managerial purposes only.
EUBIF	Eubif	European GBIF Nodes.
Work package 11	wp11	Multi-lingual access.
Work package 12	wp12	Information services on European biodiversity data.
Work package 13	wp13	Making non-European biodiversity data in European repositories globally available.

Work package 4	Wp4	IPR, copyrights & financial issues
wp2p	wp2-p	Partners for ENBI forums

A clickable version of this road map is available on line at
<http://www.enbi.info/forums/ig/repository.php>

5. Discussions and conclusions of:

1. First ENBI e-conference. Open-access for biodiversity information

Discussing the issue of sharing biodiversity information arises several obvious questions:

- Why sharing biodiversity Information?
- What to share?
- How to share it in an efficient way?

A list of topics was provided by the organizers of the e-conference:

- a. Problems and advantages of sharing information
- b. Sharing of data for profit or for free?
- c. Are different levels of access acceptable or convenient?
- d. How data providers can protect their rights. Are good will and "conditions and provisos for use of content" enough?
- e. Should users of Biodiversity information be registered?
- f. How to encourage data sharing?
- g. It is sensible to expect free access to private collections?

After the developing of the present e-conferences a pull of different conclusions was gathered with the opinions of the participants with the provided discussions topics:

a. Advantages and problems of sharing information

Advantages:

- Sharing information gives added value to the data, they can be seen and discussed, comments can be submitted by experts and questions can arise. Knowledge gaps can be identified.
- Sharing information enhances collaboration and enables to work in a multidisciplinary context.
- Sharing information in an efficient and adapted way for the different target end-users enables to the different actors to better evaluate the situations and take decisions, elaborate policies, which match better the real needs.
- Sharing information in an open and user-friendly way through the internet may touch a wider public and increase consciousness of the importance of biodiversity related issues.

Problems:

- There is such a huge mass of data, so how to interlink these data in the most efficient way? Is it possible to have a central access point and track back the wanted information in an easy and quick way?
- Considering this huge amount of data, is it possible to guarantee the accuracy of the data shared and shown online? Are efficient validation tools available and realistic at longer term with the growing data volume? Can we be sure that the end-user will not get lost? Will it not take to much computer time to find the wanted answers?
- How can the data providers rights be efficiently protected, how to guarantee the security and minimize the misuse of the data? Biodiversity data acquire value for publication with

time, for example, if sampling is repeated over several years. Data about endangered species or dangerous bacteria strains are collected. Is it safe to share such data, which are important for biodiversity research but where a risk of misuse exists?

- b. Sharing of data for profit or for free
 - GBIF principle is to make biodiversity data freely available to all, adding the issue of profit might spoil the whole idea. Now we of course all agree that collecting such data is as well time and cost effective. There is a prize to pay for human and technical resources. These costs might be paid by public and/or private funds, by the selling of the products issued from the correct usage of the information shared. There should be an agreement on minimal but enough informative data to be accessible freely.
- c. Are different levels of access acceptable or convenient?
 - Different level of access can offer some guarantees for private or sensible data, but requests more complicated IT developments. And how to be sure of the security at longer term? To get things going, a solution might be to focus first on non sensible data and deal with different access levels later, but the basic IT tools used, should be designed in such a way that security can be added afterwards without having to reorganized all the work done.
- d. How can data providers protect their rights. Are good will and "conditions and provisions for use of content" enough?
 - This is a matter of mutual trust, difficult to assess, which brings us to the previous point of different access levels
 - Data providers have also a responsibility here by being aware of the importance of submitting accurate and up to date metadata along with their data. Regular upgrades are necessary. Efficient technologies exist to link each data to its owner(s), but there is nothing we can do to respect IPR properly, if the metadata are not provided and regularly updated.
- e. Should users of Biodiversity information be registered?
 - Yes this can be very interesting to make statistics of usages, give feed-back to end-users and lowers the temptation of an misuse of the data.
- f. How to encourage data sharing
 - By showing the added value and usefulness with a few good chosen examples
 - By being aware of end-users needs and try to fulfil real needs and gaps
- g. It is sensible to expect free access to private collections?
 - Definitely, passionate people often hold private collections and the collections tend unfortunately to get lost or be dispersed.
 - Must also show them the added value of sharing the information, getting known, guaranty that their work or possession will not get lost, guaranty that their name will always be associated with the data...

*Reliability of biodiversity information:

Sharing information obviously is fundamental to biodiversity science and conservation. However, insufficient attention is given to the development of effective and efficient validation techniques and tools. These are crucial to the use of the information, especially taking into account the overwhelming amount of available data. Development of

such tools should therefore be a high priority. Ultimately, it may be necessary to restrict access to data of dubious accuracy.

*Aspects of harmonisation and standardisation:

Data quality can be assessed by the source. Sharing information implies data should be comparable and harmonised in order to be relevant and useful for the users.

Making explicit the link between collection data and "project" data in databases may contribute to suit users' needs.

To respect IPR it is essential to link each data presented online to its source(s). From a technical point of view using multiple parent IDs in the metadata standards for example can solve the issue of multiple sources for a collection. But the issue of assessing the quality of the data by its source(s) remains open.

*Data reliability and completeness vs. storage. Why losing information? :

Reducing the information to be stored in GBIF may prevent us to carry out several assessments and analyses in the future. Thus, we have to find a way to store virtually all available information, but also not saturating GBIF. I propose to relate any specimen stored in GBIF to a unique number, and decentralize information storage.

A unique accession number for specimens?.

*Qualifying data is a problem, data storage is not:

Access to information not directly web-available may help to separate two kinds of users, and would still be rapid.

*A unique, invariable, reference for each specimen is desirable.

* A stable part - GPS Georeference.

Including both exact GPS locations, as well as taxonomic information, in the single-specimen-code, would result in losing its utility. Once GBIF is working, the generation of such a code will be a very easy and rapid task.

Some topics might need further discussions:

Data quantity vs. Data quality (need for validation tools) Implication of all actors, not just scientists What type of unique identifier for specimens: human understandable code or automatically and centrally generated number?

2. *Second ENBI e-conference. Data Validation and Restrictions in the GBIF network.*

Five issues can be considered under the topic of access criteria, the first three being more relevant to all users, the last two particularly to taxonomists:

1. Controlled access to sensitive data, such as those on endangered species and exploitable natural resources.
2. Controlled access to imprecise, uncertain, and unreliable data, such as identification and location; also of importance here is the question as to how to proceed with missing data and warn users.
3. Different access for different users, do we need a user registry system?
4. Special specimens: e.g., types, historically important material. It is a convention of the codes of nomenclature that types "are the property of science", which implies that access to data about them should always be free to bona fide researchers.
5. Specimens in the process of being described as new taxa: a specialized taxonomic type of sensitive data.

After the developing of the present e-conferences a pull of different conclusions was gathered with the opinions of the participants with the provided discussions topics:

*Data quality definition:

What is "quality of data"? It is suggested that Quality = Reliability + Accuracy. Is it more complex than that? Is there a difference between "data of good quality" and "validated or checked data"?

For these two words, Reliability + Accuracy, certainly defines GOOD quality data. Quality is also assessed by the reliability (reputation) of the person or institution. There can be many human factors affecting the quality of data.

The assessment of the reliability of the author of the data is one of the component of the reliability. For instance, the reliability of a character state in a description depends also on the nature of the character, whatever the author is. Also, it has to do if we need to assess the quality field by field, or the record as a whole. Maybe other parts of reliability are to be raised when discussing how to assess.

Needs of metadata. It is important that the 'data collector' if he is not the researcher, must be aware of the logic behind the purpose of data collection. It is extremely important that every dataset is "described" by metadata. Utilising metadata the user is able to judge if the data set is "good enough" [for a given purpose].

Quality is thus only a part of metadata. Is it possible to propose a guideline if not a standard for these metadata?

Repeatability and cross-checking: A data of good quality I think is also reinforced with validation from other people thru similar works.

Also, 'repeatability' can be used to determine the accuracy of some types of data. Comparison of data from different sources can throw light on reliability; in the real world, all data are amenable to interpretation; so analysis and interpretation can be used as a tool to determine data reliability.

Has it to do with how to assess?

**How to assess biodiversity databases?*

**Is it useful to validate or check or peer-review biodiversity databases?*

** Needs for quality assessment*

Should this forum recommend to deliver raw delivered on the web data as quickly as possible, because we generally lack data, or to have a minimum control on what is delivered and how and to whom?

**Restriction to data access. User categories:*

Should different kinds of users have different access rights? In other words, should the access be restricted with respect to the data quality? Or should we only warn users of poor quality data, and suggested restricted uses? If restrictions are retained, how many (and which) user categories should include such system? Who, and how, should evaluate the access category given to each user? Is it necessary to manage a registry system?

**Special restrictions.*

3. First ENBI Forums workshop (Prague) Promoting Access to Biodiversity Information: balancing needs of users and providers

As the contributions to the 1st ENBI electronic conference (2003) were not as numerous as expected, ENBI Forums decided to postpone the 1st WS (M2.3), and unite its budget with the one for the 2nd WS (M2.5). This meeting (Prague, 25th to 28th May 2004) did feed from the outcome of both e-conferences, maximizing the cost/effectiveness of travel, accommodation and organization of such an event, and allowing us to invite more stakeholders to this forum.

The first ENBI Forums workshop took place from 25th to 28th May 2004, under the title "Promoting Access to Biodiversity Information: balancing needs of users and providers". The topic for this First ENBI Forums Workshop derived from the issues raised during the First and Second ENBI e-conferences: Open-access for biodiversity information (8 - 28th September 2003) and Data Validation and Restrictions in the GBIF network (9 - 24th March 2004), respectively. The workshop gathered together 29 participants from 15 countries. Worthwhile to mention was the strong participation from "EU new member countries". Their presentations proved to be an eye opening experience, and illustrated quite well the different approaches and needs of these countries in relation to GBIF. The participation of Donald Hobern --GBIF officer for Data Access and Database Interoperability-- was especially relevant. Donald Hobern provided first-hand information on the architecture of the GBIF network, future directions and related issues. Besides, his input in the discussions was very helpful and important factor in the overall success of the meeting. The presentations and reports of the workshop are available at ENBI Forums (WP2) web pages (<http://www.enbi.info/forums/ws1/index.php>) and in ENBI-CIRCA Community Library at (<http://circa.gbif.net/Public/irc/enbi/ws1/library>).

Breakout Conclusions :

Quality

Technical validation tools

Tools to assist content validation

Need for feed-back mechanisms, not a technical problem but

How to encourage feed-back? Involve user financially? More interest, have an investment

Quality on the service and content, Service responsibility of GBIF, National Nodes ...

Content data quality responsibility of dataproviders

Quantity should not be an issue, even imprecise data has its use

Define users and User Needs (EHNSIN)

Problems of nomenclature and synonymy, able to access synonyms,

Define source of nomenclature when providing scientific Names, Be part of the metadata ?

Accommodating alternative classifications for a same Taxa (ECAT, ILDS), crosschecking with nomenclators

Debate about a reliability flag on different datasets

Responsibility of the users if he wants to use the data.

Commercial Exploitation ?

Difficult to distinguish between non-profit and commercial use of data

Difficult to apply charging system

Public funding agencies and governments drive to public access

Level of definition can always be controlled by the data supplier (control what they publish)

Perceived threat of exploitation of their data if give public access

UK: increased open access increase collaboration

Income generation may be necessary for survival and long term maintenance

Problem of long term maintenance for data providers and the national nodes

Charging for administrative costs may be acceptable, not for the data

Charge for specific user needs and other services, interpretation of data

Registering portals at GBIF, but not of users

GBIF concentrating on free data and other levels of access with the providers

Need for generic portal tool kit.

For national nodes
For Data Providers
For thematic groups
Easily customisable

4. *Third ENBI e-conference. Improving European participation in GBIF*

The third ENBI e-conference (M2.6), carried out at month 26, took place from 14th to 28th February 2005, under the title “Improving European participation in GBIF”. One hundred and sixty one people participated to this conference and 58 messages were posted on the discussion list along of the e-conference period, apart from the 12 commented several questions daily posted by Dr. Yde de Jong, moderator of the e-conference.

The e-conference was divided into three sections, the first dealing with Europe in GBIF: what it is, what it can be, Countries that are not yet members of GBIF, how can scientific activities from non-member countries be incorporated into GBIF and which relevance European activities/projects are not incorporated in GBIF. The second section dealing with systematics and conservation community of GBIF and Integration and use of heterogeneous data and, finally, the last section dealing with the problem or solution of the GBIF European node: continuity issue of some European initiatives, the way to incorporate activities from non-GBIF countries, Clearinghouse for European GBIF nodes Those topics were further discussed in a two days third session.

Full contents of this second ENBI *e-conference* are available at ENBI Forums (WP2) web pages (<http://www.enbi.info/forums/ec3/index.php>) and ENBI Community Library at CIRCA (<http://circa.gbif.net/Public/irc/enbi/econ3/library>).

5. *Second ENBI Forums workshop (Palma de Mallorca). Improving European participation in GBIF: The participants' point of view*

The second ENBI Forums workshop took place from 10th to 12th May 2005, under the title “Improving European participation in GBIF”. The topic for this Second ENBI Forums Workshop derived from the issues raised during the First, Second and Third ENBI e-conferences: “Open-access for biodiversity information” (8 - 28th September 2003), “Data Validation and Restrictions in the GBIF network” (9 - 24th March 2004), and “Improving European participation in GBIF” (14- 28th February 2005) respectively. The workshop gathered together 24 participants from 13 countries. Worthwhile we want to mention as in the first workshop, the strong participation from "EU new member countries". Their presentations probed to be an eye opening experience, and illustrated quite well the different approaches and needs of these countries in relation to GBIF.

The presentations and reports of the workshop are available at ENBI Forums (WP2) web pages (<http://www.enbi.info/forums/ws2/index.php>) and in ENBI-CIRCA Community Library at (<http://circa.gbif.net/Public/irc/enbi/ws2/library>).

6. Conclusions, remarks, lessons learned

The focus of WP2, ENBI Forums, has been to provide the instruments to allow institutions, projects and individuals in Europe with an interest in Biodiversity Information to know of each other, to contact each other and, in short, to form a network.

Having a clear focus on professionals, the task of opening new horizons for mutual learning and collaboration is a difficult task. The daily demands are very high, and prioritization is a necessity; anything not resulting in a project, a paper or a grant gets very little attention. Under these conditions, three years is too short for such a process. A networking platform for biodiversity information in Europe should last not longer, but be permanent resource at the service of the community.

In these three years, we have walked a way from not having a real idea of what to do and how, to enjoy some interesting and productive events such as the workshop held in Palma earlier this year. We learnt that to provide a platform does not mean that people are going to use it right away. We learnt to use it ourselves and to convince people that it could be beneficial for them too. We learnt the power and the limitations of electronic conferences. We met excellent and generous professionals, such as the ones that coordinated the e-conferences, who shared with us their knowledge and their talent.

The workshops provided a discussion and learning space for GBIF node managers and other (stake)holders of biodiversity information in Europe. To meet and discuss with people is the first necessary step for collaboration, and some of such have been initiated under the umbrella of ENBI. From the comparison of the communications, reports and presentations from the first year to the third, it is clear that the community, part of it at least, has also learnt to network, a reason to be satisfied.

At the end all that we learned from working for ENBI Forums, will stay with us. However, the end of ENBI means that the potential of what have been achieved so far will remain unrealized. Let us hope and work for a not-to-distant reincarnation of the networking platform that ENBI has provided for the biodiversity information community in Europe.

Once the project is finalized it is intended to keep providing access and maintenance to the ENBI web site and CIRCA ENBI space. In that regard, a proposal has been developed to tackle the continuation of these ENBI services properly for the next five years.

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